

Speculation on Entropy in Terms of a Maximum Number of Measurements Part 2

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In Part I, we tried to argue that thermodynamic entropy contained in the first law of thermodynamics is linked to information entropy, at least for the volume features for an ideal gas. Here, we try to demonstrate this in another manner making use of the ideal gas law. In particular, we try to show that the ideal gas law ultimately leads to the form dV/V which is part of information theory. This form, however, appears in the $d\text{Work} = -PdV$ term, but we show that this is related to delta heat, and so delta heat becomes associated with information theory. Finally, we show that one does not really need the ideal gas law directly, but that volume scaling leads to the information theoretic form dV/V because $E(T)$.

Ideal Gas and the First Law of Thermodynamics

As noted in Part I, the first law of thermodynamics is a conservation of energy equation which contains a delta heat term showing that one can change energy without doing mechanical work. This is physically manifested by a gas becoming hotter if one lets it absorb photons while keeping its volume fixed. If the gas only consists of molecules, then one might guess that temperature is a parameter related to average kinetic energy as there seems to be no other energy in the container. In such a case, $E(T)$ and not of volume because kinetic energy of molecules is not linked to the size of the box which contains them. (This is the ideal gas law simplification.) Now, if energy can only be expressed through kinetic energy of molecules, then work done compressing the box to a smaller volume must result in both a change in volume and temperature. Thus, a temperature change is not a signature of heat flow, but rather of energy change. A heat flow means that the temperature changes without the volume changing. For the case of a pure heat flow:

$$dE = 3/2 nR dT = \text{delta heat} \quad ((1))$$

Thus, in this case, delta heat = $f(T) dT$ with no volume present because there is no volume on the LHS. On the other hand, if there is no heat (no photons coming in), but volume changes through work so that:

$$dE = -PdV \quad ((2)) \quad \text{then} \quad 3/2 NR dT = -P(T,V) dV \quad ((2))$$

This shows how dV must be a function of dT in this case. It also means that delta heat cannot simply be a function of T . It must be of the form:

$$\text{Delta heat} = f_1(T) dT + f_2(V) dV \quad ((3))$$

For the case of $((2))$, dV is linked with dT and so the two terms of $((3))$ must cancel as there is no heat flow.

At this point, one deals with thermodynamics and there seems to be no sense of information theory or entropy. One has two seemingly clear variables T and V which are interrelated in ((2)). In other words, delta heat is not at all linked with probability or $\ln(\text{number of states})$ etc

If one considers the ideal gas law: $PV=nRT$, obtained experimentally by Boyle, then one observes an interesting feature:

$$dE = \frac{3}{2} nRdT = -nRT \frac{dV}{V} \quad ((4)) \quad (\text{from } ((2)))$$

$$\text{Now } -\frac{dV}{V} = -d \ln(V) = d \ln(1/V) \quad ((5))$$

In this case, $1/V$ is a probability and $\ln(1/V)$ is information, i.e. \ln of a probability. As a result, one sees a direct link with information theory, but in the work term. This suggests that:

$$\frac{3}{2} \frac{dT}{T} = d \ln(T^{\frac{3}{2}}) = d \ln(1/V) \quad ((6))$$

means that $\ln(T^{\frac{3}{2}})$ also represents a probability linked with finding single particle energy within the average energy E if $1/V$ is the probability to find a single particle at an x,y,z point.

The delta heat term, too, is influenced by these two probabilistic terms.

In ((3)), $f_1(T) dT = \frac{3}{2} nR dT$ for the case of photon absorption with no V change. In the case of no heat with dV changing, one must have:

$$0 = \frac{3}{2} nRdT + f_2(V)dV \quad ((7))$$

The first term on the RHS of ((7)) is just dE , so the second term must be PdV so that the case of no heat flow yields ((7)). Thus:

$$f_2(V) = P = nRT/V \quad ((8))$$

Thus ((3)) becomes: delta heat proportional to $T nR \{ d \ln(T^{\frac{3}{2}}) + d \ln(V) \}$ ((9))

In other words, the two information theory terms from $dE = -PdV$ are now present in the delta heat term, demonstrating that it is based on information theory for an ideal gas.

As a result, one may use thermodynamic arguments without any notion of entropy or microscopic classical statistical mechanics (except for the qualitative assumption that $E =$ average kinetic energy because no quantitative probability distribution is used) to find ((9)), i.e. that delta heat is based on information theory for an ideal gas.

General Example of Information Theory

Information theory seems to apply readily to the toss of a coin or die which is not at all linked with any energy conservation equation or first law of thermodynamics. One thus finds a

Shannon's entropy or informational entropy based on the probability present in the problem, but this probability is exactly of the form of $1/V$ in the ideal gas treatment, i.e. $1/2$ for a coin and $1/6$ for a die. This begs the question: Why should information theory considerations appear in a delta heat term which should simply describe a change in energy not linked with a change in V (volume). The fact that $\delta \text{heat} = f_1(T) dT + f_2(V) dV$ does not imply information theory. T and V are simply two variables in the system. It seems that it is the ideal gas law $PV=nRT$ which introduces the idea of dV/V which creates a direct link to information theory (as well as the T which may combine with dT in dT/T , also indicating information theory). We, however, wish to see if there is a more general idea present.

Given: $dE = 3/2nR dT = P(T,V) dV$ ((10)), one may see that: $dV = \text{constant } dT / P(T,V)$. In other words, the change in volume is proportional to the change in energy divided by Pressure. Pressure is Force/Area, so the change in dV is such that it erases the presence of P , (the force/Area), leaving only constant dT . The key idea, however, seems to be scaling of volume. Given ((10)), one may see that scaling volume on the LHS does nothing because it does not appear. Scaling volume on the right hand side must have the same effect, so one expects:

$$PdV = f_3(T) dV/V \quad ((11))$$

This scaling feature, however, directly yields an information theoretic term. Thus, even if one did not know the ideal gas law, one would suggest dV/V from scaling arguments, and hence the presence of information theory in delta heat for an ideal gas.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that information theoretic ideas like Shannon's information entropy = $-k \sum P(i) \ln(P(i))$, where $P(i)$ is the probability for event i , appear in examples such as the toss of a coin or die. What might seem surprising is that they also appear in an energy conservation equation (the first law of thermodynamics) $dE = \delta \text{heat} + \delta \text{Work}$. Here heat is defined as a change in energy, holding V (volume) constant as $\delta \text{Work} \rightarrow -P(T,V) dV$, where $P(T,V)$ is pressure. The ideal gas situation is that: $E(T)$. This means that for no heat, $dE = \text{constant } dT = -P(T,V)dV$. There is no V on the LHS and so scaling V on the RHS must lead to a cancellation of the scale factor. Thus, one has: $P(T,V) = f(T)/V$. This immediately yields $dV/V = -d \ln(1/V)$ which is an expression from information theory with $1/V$ representing probability. Given that this appears in the work term, we have shown above that it also becomes part of the delta heat term and so this term is also linked with information theory. Thus, in the case of an ideal gas $E(T)$ (no volume), one sees information theoretical ideas present.